

Exploring Health Message Memorability among University Students: A Quantitative Survey of COVID-19 Pandemic Prevention Communication in Jammu and Kashmir, India

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Abstract: To prepare students to begin attending classes in-person in the universities of Jammu and Kashmir (J&K) during the receding phase of the COVID-19 pandemic, students often received many preventive care messages advising them how to prevent the spread of the novel Coronavirus. This study explores the use of memorable messages about pandemic prevention and their influences on the behaviors of university students in J&K. A quantitative survey was conducted with 167 students from the two selected universities who were randomly selected to a representative sample. Questionnaires using close-ended questions were distributed and completed online by university students. Results revealed that most participants' memorized information about preventive measures in response to their repeated dissemination to reduce risks of contagion from the coronavirus. Survey responses suggested that the prevention messages were evaluated by student as being clear and concise, and messages were highly effective in encouraging adoption of prevention behavior among the university students. In addition, the survey found that students relied on a mix of official (government agencies) and unofficial (media, social media) sources for COVID-19 information. This study contributes to important knowledge about health communication during the COVID-19 pandemic to evaluate the effectiveness of prevention messages to safely reintegrate students to taking in-person classes. Insights from this study may help health policymakers design effective messages for addressing future health emergencies.

Keywords: Health communication, memorable messages, Covid-19 pandemic, University students, Jammu and Kashmir.

Introduction:

Dangerous infectious diseases have the potential to appear unexpectedly and if neglected, can spread widely into pandemics. They often are unpredictable (Gully, 2020) and can emerge suddenly, resulting in devastating consequences (Looi, 2023; Janecka, 2021). In the face of a pandemic, meaningful and adaptive prevention communication responses from all public institutions to manage contagion and illness is imperative (Gully, 2020; Kreps, 2024; 2021). Establishing effective communication processes to promote prevention is pivotal to reduce contagion during pandemics (Kim & Kreps, 2020) to shape public opinion and influence health behaviors (Aziz, 2021). Along with other medical emergency practices to curtail the transmission of viruses, reliable, timely, and trustworthy health communication can have a resounding influence on building trust to calm the public (Parson et al, 2017) and to alter the perception of people, resulting in better health outcomes (Fifolt et al, 2024). At the heart of impactful communication lies the indelibility of health messages (Koinig, 2021) as ambiguous and fragmented mes-

sages devoid of precision result in non-mnemonic effects thus leading to confusion and fear among people (Melo, 2020). Transparent and continuous health communication is imperative during challenging times (Wallis, P. & Nerlich, 2005) as it contributes to pandemic vigilance (Burkle, 2023). Box-Steffensmeier, (2021) further recognizes that memorable health messages significantly aid in shaping the perception and behavior of the public hence, substantially aiding in efforts to contain pandemics (Almeida, 2019). Kuang, 2021, further underscores that memorable health messages bolster an individual's ability to navigate dangers as they provide empowerment and guidance in fostering anticipatory resilience. Sutton, (2015) emphasizes the effectiveness of precise and terse messages, especially those disseminated through social media, and advocates, that they prove fruitful in endowing actionable guidelines during health emergencies.

Gupta (2021) emphasized the role of communication found that in developing countries, there is a greater need for effective communication during a health crisis. Since India's health infrastructure in comparison to the developed world is weaker (Aggarwal, 2015; Shastri, 2016; Mann, 2020), the situation in Jammu and Kashmir is not encouraging. Mahase (2019) and Pandov (2021) imply that the state of Jammu and Kashmir being geographically isolated encounters added communication hurdles. Commenting on the healthcare system of Jammu and Kashmir, (Qadir, 2013) see it as poor, attributing it to inadequate medical facilities. Bhat et.al (2021) observed a prevalent lack of knowledge and awareness among the people of Kashmir, owing to a lack of effective communication and pitched for better health communication during a pandemic akin to covid-19. For enhanced effectiveness of health messages for demography like India, Sultana (2021) advocates that to make health information more effective, accurate, short, and memorable approaches are vital. The recent COVID-19 outbreak has also highlighted an urgency for effective health communication (Kreps, 2020) and effective health communication mandates concise, iterated, and tailored messages in remedying health crisis (Ratzan, 2001; Kukafka, 2005) thereby serving in influencing public behavior and to shape their memory (Taylor, 2022). COVID-19 has also demonstrated that during a pandemic, misinformation surges, thus fueling panic among people (Kim & Kreps, 2021; Prokopenko, Shcherbachenko, & Kulibaba, 2020) and the remedy to overcome this misinformation and panic buying is to disseminate clear, concise, and memorable messages (Martel, 2021 and Vraga, 2020). The significance of tailored and memorable health texts aids in greater cognitive involvement and improved message relevance (Kreuter, 2003; Noar, 2009). The present research identifies the health information sources during the COVID-19 pandemic in Jammu and Kashmir. It underscores the importance of tailoring precise health messages, as well as justifying its sustenance in transcultural adaptation. Furthermore, the study hints at the significant step of established health communication in the recent COVID-19 pandemic toward improving health communication for combating to virus by reaching out to a diverse population.

Significance of Research:

Globally a lot has been explored about the health message innovation and their impact on ground level. However, which sources remained more likely common for health message seeking and factors for health message memorability among students in India particularly in a peripheral region like Jammu and Kashmir still warrant more rigorous investigations. The research attempted to explore the sources of information and most preventive care memorable messages in health

crises like covid-19 virus. This research exemplifies the impact of preventive care messages on the behavior of university students during the COVID-19 crisis. This study contributes to important knowledge about health communication during the COVID-19 pandemic to evaluate the effectiveness of prevention messages to safely reintegrate students into taking in-person classes. Insights from this study may help health policymakers design effective messages for addressing future health emergencies.

Material and Method for Quantitative Research: This study conducted a quantitative survey with a questionnaire to elicit insights from university students in Jammu and Kashmir concerning their recollection of health messages. The University of Kashmir and the University of Jammu were selected to recruit student respondents based on their high enrolment of students and their early resumption of offline class work during the declining mode of covid-19 pandemic. In this method, the study conducted an online survey and distributed a close-ended questionnaire to achieve the objectives of the study.

The study used the close-ended questionnaire as a key instrument to facilitate the respondents with a set of predefined multiple choice answers. This allows researcher to yield statistical results from data analysis efficiently. To maintain the reliability and validity the survey form was discussed with different academicians and scholars of University.

Participants: The researcher surveyed two of main oldest universities of Jammu and Kashmir. The students have been chosen randomly from both universities, comprising both males and females. The total number of participants selected for this study is 167. The reasons for the selection of university students are their attendance of offline classes in the region, literacy, capability of understanding the message and their experiences in Covid-19 situation.

The study selected two universities from two different regions based on geographical differences, and then randomly chose students from these universities to achieve a total sample size of 167. This method ensures that the sample represents the population of students from regional diversity equally. The random selection of respondents within each university supported the avoid a bias, ensuring that every respondent had an equal chance of being included in the sample. From each selected university, randomly chosen students were chosen to achieve a combined total of 167 participants, which was determined through a sample calculator over the total enrolment of 20552 students with a 7.6% margin of error.

Research Questions:

1. What were the prominent sources of Covid-19 information among university students of Jammu and Kashmir?
2. What were instrumental factors for memorable message among these students?
3. What is the impact of memorable messages on the health behaviour university students with respect Covid-19 pandemic?

Research Objectives:

1. To know the prominent sources of Covid-19 information among students in J&K
2. To explore the contributing factors for memorable messages among these students?
3. To know the influence of memorable messages on the behaviour of University students in Jammu and Kashmir

Analysis:

Prominent Source of Covid-19 Information among students of Jammu and Kashmir					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Government health agencies	52	31.1	31.1	31.1
	Social media platforms	43	25.7	25.7	56.9
	Media outlets (Newspapers, TV, Radio, Brochures)	54	32.3	32.3	89.2
	Healthcare professionals and experts	18	10.8	10.8	100.0
	Total	167	100.0	100.0	

Prominent source of Covid-19 Information among students of Jammu and Kashmir: The analyzed data demonstrates that Media outlets (Newspapers, TV, Radio, Brochures) remained the prominent source of information with 32.3% of students surveyed, representing high level of confidence in such reports. Government health agencies ranked at second with 31.1% people seeking information from them. The prominence of Social media platforms for diffusing critical public health information on COVID-19 accounted for about a quarter of the responses standing at 25.7%. Moreover, the survey found that healthcare professionals and experts were the least preferred source of information with only 10.8% respondents trusting them.

COVID-19 message resonates the most with respondents					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Information about preventive measures	91	54.5	54.5	54.5
	Personal stories of individuals affected	32	19.2	19.2	73.7
	Statistics and data on the virus	10	6.0	6.0	79.6
	Guidance from healthcare authorities	34	20.4	20.4	100.0
	Total	167	100.0	100.0	

Resonance of COVID-19 message with students of Jammu and Kashmir: Analysis of the data on COVID-19 indicate that the communication which focused on preventive healthcare resonated most among the university students with 54.5% responding positively to such health messages. It was also found that 19.2% of the messages related to personal narratives of the Covid-19 affected individuals resonated with the people surveyed. The health communication messages diffused through Statistics and visualization on the COVID-19 pandemic exhibited a limited resonance, at 6.0%. This indicates a glaring contrast highlighting that the im-

fact of statistical messages was significantly lower as compared to preventive care health messages in building lasting impressions among the students.

Most memorable messages/slogan's about COVID-19 virus among students					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Do Gaz Ki Doori, Mask Hai Zaroori" (Maintain Two Yards of Distance, It's Essential)	27	16.2	16.2	16.2
	Ghar Pe Raho, Surakshit Raho" (Stay at Home, Stay Safe)	33	19.8	19.8	35.9
	Tika Lagao, Corona Bhagao" (Get Vaccinated, Chase Away Corona)	36	21.6	21.6	57.5
	Hathon Ki Safai, Corona Se Bachai" (Clean Hands, Safe Hands)	71	42.5	42.5	100.0
	Total	167	100.0	100.0	

Most perceived memorable COVID-19 preventive messages/slogans:

A significant proportion of the students surveyed (42.5%), recall a specific message "*Hathon Ki Safai, Corona Se Bachai*" (Clean Hands, Safe Hands) about the containment of Corona virus. This strong recall suggests that this particular message has been effective in shaping their perception towards health practices during Covid-19. It's deeply rooted resonance reinforced essential hygiene behaviors among the students to curtail the virus spread during the pandemic. Following closely, another most memorable message among individuals (21.6%) is "*Tika Lagao, Corona Bhagao*" (Get Vaccinated, Chase Away Corona), indicating the second influential slogan that is still remembered by the respondents. Out of the total respondents surveyed, a distinct group comprising of 19.4% continue to recall another specific message, "*Ghar pe Raho, Surakshit Raho*" (Stay at home, Stay safe). Additionally, 16.2 % of the respondents exhibited a strong likelihood of recalling a preventive healthcare message like "*Do Ghaz Ki Doori, Mask Hai Zaroori*" (Maintain two yards of distance, wear masks)

In summary, the findings underscore the diverse patterns of pandemic health message re membrane within surveyed university students, ranging from most memorable message "*Ghar Pe Raho, Surakshit Raho*" (Stay at Home, Stay Safe) to "*Hathon Ki Safai, Corona Se Bachai*" (Clean Hands, Safe Hands), "*Ghar Pe Raho, Surakshit Raho*" (Stay at Home, Stay Safe) and "*Do Gaz Ki Doori, Mask Hai Zaroori*". These findings emphasize the enduring impact of targeted public health messaging utilized during Covid-19 in aiding containment of the virus.

Responsive key message elements for ever lasting memory of Covid-19 information					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Clarity of information	123	73.7	73.7	73.7
	Emotional resonance	28	16.8	16.8	90.4
	Communication style	16	9.6	9.6	100.0
	Total	167	100.0	100.0	

Responsive key message elements for ever lasting memory of Covid-19 information: The data signifies that the majority of respondents (73.7%) believe that clarity of information contributed majorly in memorizing the Covid-19 information. A significant proportion (34.1%) of the students surveyed indicated that repetition of the messages helped them to memorize health messages which were followed by the conciseness of messaging at 31.7%. A substantial share of the respondents (16.8%) confirmed that the emotional content played a significant role in aiding recall. They acknowledged that emotionally charged messages leave a lasting impression as it aids in enhancing their capability to recollect key health messages. A smaller proportion, (9.2%) indicated that communication style helped them in remembrance of messages about Covid-19 preventive measures. This suggests that information precision is significant in influencing the individual's behavior and memory in remembering the information. Interactive elements such as questions and polls were perceived as least impactful, chosen by only 6% of respondents. Interestingly, 9.6% of respondents selected "others," suggesting that some impactful elements made the message's influence strong.

Overall, the findings underscore some key contributory factors for message remembrance within surveyed university students, ranging from most clarity of information to emotional resonance and communication style.

Productive role of celebrities in health message diffusion and memorising					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very ineffective	27	16.2	16.2	16.2
	Ineffective	20	12.0	12.0	28.1
	Neutral	31	18.6	18.6	46.7
	Effective	44	26.3	26.3	73.1
	Very effective	45	26.9	26.9	100.0
	Total	167	100.0	100.0	

Productive role of celebrities in health message diffusion and memorising: The analyzed data shows that celebrity endorsement of health messages plays a significant role in making communication effective. Almost 52.7% of respondents affirm that celebrity involvement in recalling and memorizing messages plays a crucial role, stressing upon the influence public figures exert in enhancing message retention. While their role in making health messages appealing and effective is widely acknowledged, a small proportion of the respondents however remain resistant to this belief. This variability in public perception is derived from the fact that nearly 19% of the respondents perceived their role neutrally while as a small portion nullified their role in health message remembrance.

Prompting actions by memorable message					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	55	32.9	32.9	32.9
	Strongly agree	46	27.5	27.5	60.5
	Neutral	66	39.5	39.5	100.0
	Total	167	100.0	100.0	

Prompting actions by memorable message: Majority of the respondents (60.4% agree and strongly agree) agreed that memorable messages prompted them to take specific actions to curtail the spread of virus during the pandemic. However, the largest single category was "Neutral" at 39.5%, suggesting that a significant portion of the population was either unsure about the impact of these messages on their actions or felt the impact was moderate. Notably, the study found no responses in the "Disagree" or "Strongly disagree" categories. The absence of responses in favour of (disagree/strongly disagree) suggests that even if the messages didn't always prompt action, they were not perceived as ineffective or counterproductive.

This data specifies that memorable messages can prove an effective tool in health communications, particularly in boosting action during a pandemic. However, the responses in favour of neutral also suggest there may be room for development in message planning to increase its action-prompting effectiveness across a broader segment of the population.

Conclusion: The research findings provide valuable insights into crafting health messages during health emergencies akin to Covid-19. It offers a roadmap by emphasizing that clarity, repetition and individual anecdotes significantly influences the process of message retention compared to raw statistics and figures. It also underscores that the creation of engaging content centered on concise and rhythmic patterns during public health campaigns is the key to achieve desired outcomes. Take for instance this particular message, "*Hathon Ki Safai, Corona Se Bachai*"(Clean Hands, Safe Hands). The analysis revealed that a significant majority of respondents reported that this message had a high influence on their understanding and played an effective in conveying the gravity of the situation. It amply specifies that well-crafted health messages boost memorability and compels diverse audience to act upon. Moreover, the findings indicate that those messages which were repetitive and preventive in nature were the most resonating within the respondents. Although it emerged that students relied on a mix of official (government agencies) and unofficial (social media) sources for COVID-19 information but a notable finding was that traditional (print & electronic) media still have a strong influence in disseminating critical public health information.

The study found students relied on a mix of official (government agencies) and unofficial (media, social media) sources for COVID-19 information. Moreover, the findings demonstrate that traditional media still has a strong influence on diffusing critical public health information. Furthermore, the study found that students have a strong belief that clarity of information helped them to remember the messages about covid-19 pandemic. This suggests that message precision significantly influences the individual's behavior and memory in remembering health information. The analysis revealed that COVID-19 messages resonance among university students in Jammu and Kashmir shows preventive care COVID-19 messages are the leading resonating with university students due to their "Repetition of messages". The majority of participants remembered the messages about covid-19 pandemic are "*Hathon Ki Safai, Corona Se Bachai*"(Clean Hands, Safe Hands) with due role of celebrities in affecting on ability to recall the messages during the COVID-19 pandemic. The data found a significant majority of respondents reported that these messages had a high influence on their understanding and played an effective in conveying the gravity of the situation. This specifies that memorable messages can prove an effective tool in health communications, particularly in boosting action during a crisis like a pandemic.

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